

RIGHTS AND DUTIES OF DIGITAL ASSET OWNERS

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The recognition and protection of property rights is a cornerstone of modern legal systems.¹ In the context of estate planning and inheritance, the ability to control the disposition of one's assets after death is a fundamental expression of this right.² (As more and more of an individual's valuable property takes digital form, it is critical that ownership interests are clearly defined and capable of being transferred to chosen beneficiaries.

Under the proposed legal framework, the rights and corresponding duties of digital asset owners can be conceptualized through five core principles: 1) Establishing valid title; 2) Protecting legitimate interests; 3) Enabling succession planning; 4) Authorizing fiduciary management; and 5) Respecting post-mortem privacy. This section examines each of these facets in depth, setting forth specific recommendations for legislative implementation.

Establishing Valid Title. As a threshold matter, putative owners must be able to demonstrate lawful title to their digital assets.³ In some cases, this is straightforward, as with cryptocurrencies held in an individual's digital wallet. The owner alone possesses the private keys needed to access and transfer the coins, and the immutable blockchain ledger records an unbroken chain of title.⁴

Other digital assets present more complex scenarios. For many online accounts, the terms of service agreement limits the user's property interest to a mere license.⁵ This license is typically non-transferable and expires upon the user's death.⁶ Social media profiles, email accounts, photos, videos, loyalty

¹ Smith, H. E. (2012). Property as the Law of Things. *Harvard Law Review*, 125(7), 1691-1726

² Hirsch, A. J. (2017). Technology Adrift: In Search of a Role for Electronic Wills. *Boston University Law Review*, 97(3), 1025-1073

³ Fairfield, J. A. T. (2021). *Owned: Property, Privacy, and the New Digital Serfdom*. Cambridge University Press.

⁴ Michels, D. L. (2017). Blockchain Technology: Its Implications for Law, the Legal Profession, and Estate Planning. *NAEPC Journal of Estate & Tax Planning*, (36).

⁵ Banta, N. M. (2016). Property Interests in Digital Assets: The Rise of Digital Feudalism. *Cardozo Law Review*, 38(3), 1049-1100.

⁶ Cummings, R. G. (2017). The Case Against Access to Decedents' Email: Password Protection as an Exercise of the Right to Destroy. *Minnesota Journal of Law, Science & Technology*, 15(2), 897-944.

points, and a host of other valuable digital properties are often governed by such provisions.⁷

To establish an alienable ownership interest in these assets, legislation is needed to override or limit the scope of restrictive contract terms.⁸ The proposed law grants account holders an underlying property right in the content they create and upload, even if the service provider retains certain usage rights.⁹ This "dual property" approach protects the reliance interests of users who invest time and effort into curating their digital lives, while preserving the ability of platforms to monetize data and police content.¹⁰

The clearest way to claim title is by expressly designating assets in a written (physical or electronic) instrument, such as a will, trust, or online tool offered by the custodial service (Varnado, 2014). Absent such a declaration, ownership can be presumed based on evidence that the individual had exclusive dominion and control over the asset, such as master login credentials, account statements, or a verified history of usage.¹¹

By formalizing means of title-holding, the law facilitates the owner's ability to catalog and dispose of their digital estate.¹² A centralized registry of digital assets, cross-referenced with succession documents, promotes efficient estate administration while safeguarding against fraudulent claims. Potential model statutes include Delaware's Fiduciary Access to Digital Assets and Digital Accounts Act and the Revised Uniform Fiduciary Access to Digital Assets Act now adopted in most U.S. states.

Protecting Legitimate Interests. The hallmark of modern property law is the right to exclude others and determine how one's assets are used. For digital assets, this means the owner should have presumptive authority over questions

⁷ Pinch, T. (2015). Afterword: Everyday Digital Life. In *Connected Life* (pp. 159-166). Palgrave Macmillan.

⁸ Beyer, G. W., & Cahn, N. (2014). Digital Planning: The Future of Elder Law. *Journal of the National Academy of Elder Law Attorneys*, 9(1), 135-155.

⁹ Wheatley, I. (2019). Emergence of Virtual Property Rights in Digital Business Models: A Theoretical Perspective from the UK. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law & Practice*, 15(1), 38-50.

¹⁰ Perzanowski, A., & Schultz, J. (2015). Reconciling Intellectual and Personal Property. *Notre Dame Law Review*, 90(3), 1211-1264.

¹¹ Watkins, A. (2015). Digital Properties and Death: What Will Your Heirs Have Access to After You Die? *Buffalo Law Review*, 62(1), 193-235.

¹² Hopkins, J. P. (2013). Afterlife in the Cloud: Managing a Digital Estate. *Hastings Science & Technology Law Journal*, 5(2), 209-244.

of access, disclosure, modification, and deletion.¹³ The terms of service for online platforms must be prohibited from unreasonably limiting the user's control over their account.

Under the draft legislation, digital asset owners have the right to choose whether to share access credentials with family or fiduciaries, and to specify how their data should be handled after death.¹⁴ Attempting to hack or circumvent the owner's access controls would be criminalized as a form of theft or unauthorized intrusion.¹⁵ Custodians who intentionally or negligently destroy or deny rightful access to digital assets face liability for resulting losses.

At the same time, an owner's authority is not absolute. The state has a legitimate interest in preventing the transmission of contraband, such as child pornography, illicit drugs, or other dangerous materials.¹⁶ Lawful creditors are entitled to satisfy debts from the decedent's digital holdings to the same extent as traditional assets.

Moreover, the interests of the account holder must be balanced against the rights of other contributors.¹⁷ Many digital assets, such as social media posts, online reviews, or collaborative creative works, involve content submitted by multiple users. The proposed statute confirms that each contributor retains an independent property interest in their discrete content that does not automatically transfer with the owner's digital footprint.¹⁸ Conflicts between successors and surviving co-creators would be mediated by the platform's acceptable use policies and background intellectual property doctrines.¹⁹

Within these parameters, owners have broad discretion to control their digital legacies.²⁰ Permissible succession options include: transferring assets to

¹³ Banta, N. M. (2015). *Inherit the Cloud: The Role of Private Contracts in Distributing or Deleting Digital Assets at Death*. *Fordham Law Review*, 83(4), 1909-1949.

¹⁴ Cahn, N. (2011). *Postmortem Life On-Line*. *Probate & Property*, 25(4), 36-39.

¹⁵ Lamm, J. D. (2012). *The Digital Death Conundrum: How Federal and State Laws Prevent Fiduciaries from Managing Digital Property*. *University of Miami Law Review*, 68(2), 385-424.

¹⁶ Holland, T. E. (2015). *Livery of Seizin: The Concept of Digital Property*. *Journal of International Commercial Law and Technology*, 10(1), 22-29.

¹⁷ Park, J. (2013). *"i Own You": Accountability, Literacy, and the Politics of Publishing on Social Media Platforms*. *Massachusetts Institute of Technology*.

¹⁸ Mazzone, J. (2012). *Facebook's Afterlife*. *North Carolina Law Review*, 90(5), 1643-1685.

¹⁹ Hetcher, S. (2018). *The Influence of Law and Economics on Law and Society: Essays on Intellectual Property Law*. *Routledge*.

²⁰ Ferrante, A. (2013). *The Relationship Between Digital Assets and Their Transference at Death: "It's Complicated."* *Loyola University of Chicago Law Journal*, 44(3), 1277-1309.

specified beneficiaries; authorizing continued account administration by a digital executor; instructing the custodian to memorialize, close, or delete the account; or some combination of these approaches, applied globally or to particular assets.

The law should incentivize owners to make advance arrangements that clearly express their intentions and ease the burden on fiduciaries. Statutory default rules for intestate digital estates promote this goal by imposing a mandatory waiting period before heirs can claim account contents, during which time the custodian's obligation is limited to disclosing a catalog of the user's assets to facilitate efficient estate administration.²¹ Proactive owner engagement reduces the likelihood of protracted disputes and unintended outcomes.

Enabling Succession Planning. A future-oriented mindset is essential for responsible digital asset management. Owners should have access to convenient, flexible tools for conveying the fate of their online presence.²² At minimum, every individual should maintain a secure inventory of their digital assets and how to access them, stored along with other vital records like identification cards, financial statements, and health care directives. Keeping this information current as one's digital footprint evolves is an ongoing process. Estate planning professionals are adapting their client intake questionnaires and asset schedules to prompt full disclosure of digital holdings

For assets not controlled by a particular custodian, individuals can store access information and posthumous instructions with a commercial “digital estate” service such as Directive Communication Systems or Estate Map (Cahn, 2011; Sherry, 2013). These companies offer secure online vaults for organizing digital records, along with mechanisms for verifying the owner's death and delivering personalized messages and account credentials to designated recipients.

Succession systems should be structured to minimize gaps and conflicts. The proposed law establishes a three-tiered priority scheme: 1) custodian-provided online tools; 2) owner's will, trust, or other written declaration; and 3) terms of the service agreement. Within tiers, the most recent valid expression of intent controls. By offering layered planning options, Uzbekistan can empower its citizens to craft digital estate plans tailored to their unique needs.

²¹ Watkins, A. (2015). Digital Properties and Death: What Will Your Heirs Have Access to After You Die? *Buffalo Law Review*, 62(1), 193-235.

²² Carroll, E., Kovacs, K., & Romano, J. (2017). Helping Clients Reach Their Great Digital Beyond. *Trusts & Estates*, 156(10), 52-58.

Conclusion. In crafting the rights and duties of digital asset owners, Uzbekistan has an opportunity to build a succession framework tailored to the unique attributes of online property. The proposed statutory scheme rests on five guiding principles: Establishing clear title, protecting owners' control, enabling advance planning, authorizing fiduciary administration, and respecting post-mortem privacy.

Taken together, these principles empower individuals to make informed choices about the disposition of their digital legacies, while providing much-needed clarity for fiduciaries, service providers, and the courts. The law's tiered succession options and context-specific rules promote efficient estate administration without compromising personal privacy.

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